

Hamiltonian = pv - Lagrangian and Special Relativity

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In (1), we argued that $H=E=pv-L$ and $p=dL/dv$, where L is the relativistic free particle Lagrangian, are consistent with a quadratic form identical to $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ ($c=1$). Here, we suggest that only using $E= pv-L$ already gives a direct link to special relativity.

$H=pv-L$ and Special Relativity

We consider the free particle case for which $H=$ Hamiltonian $= E$ ((1)). We assume that L is unknown and do not use the relation: $p= dL/dv$ partial ((2))

In such a case $E = pv -L$ is a linear transformation involving E , p and v . If one assumes that L is proportional to m_0 , then rest mass is also in the picture.

We suggest that a Lorentz transformation is a linear one which converts $(0, m_0)$ in the rest frame to (p,E) as seen in a moving frame. The form of the Lorentz matrix is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v) & vg(v) \\ vg(v) & g(v) \end{vmatrix} \quad g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((3))$$

The matrix ((3)) may not only be used to convert $(0,m_0)$ ($c=1$) into (p, E) , but may also describe the reverse transformation with $v \rightarrow -v$.

Thus, applying ((3)) with v replaced with $-v$ to (p,E) yields for the second equation:

$$E' = -gvp + gE \quad ((4))$$

We set $E'=m_0cc$, rest energy in the rest frame. This equation is of the same form as $E/L - pv/L = -1$ if $L= - m_0 g(v)$ i.e.

$$M_0 = E/\sqrt{1-vv} - pv/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((5))$$

As a result, we suggest that special relativity seems to be contained as a special solution within the $H=pv-L$ equation.

The point of using H,L theory is to obtain an energy equation $E = pv-L$ and also momentum: dL/dv partial.

The question we ask is: Why should $d/dv (1/g(v))$ partial yield p ? In special relativity, one does not usually consider such a relation even though it holds mathematically.

We note that applying ((3)) to $(0,m_0)$ yields: $p= gv m_0$ ((6a)) and $E=g m_0 c^2$ ((6b))

((6a)) has a possible solution of $p = dL(v)/dv$ if L is a function of vv so that the v in gv comes from differentiating vv . Such a quadratic form for g is expected if one considers an invariant of the matrix ((3)) i.e.

$$EE - pp = m^2/c^2 \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Thus: } g(v) = -m^2/c^2 \sqrt{1 - vv/c^2} \quad ((8))$$

As a result, $g(v)$ is a candidate for creating L and in fact $-m^2/c^2 \sqrt{1 - vv/c^2}$ yields a suitable L . This, however, does not give a physical reason for using $p = dL/dv$.

Alternatively, one may consider the equation: $E = pv - L$ and note that:

$$E/L = pv/L - 1 \quad ((9))$$

For L being proportional to $-m^2/c^2 \sqrt{1 - vv/c^2}$, ((9)) may be transformed into ((7)). p , however, suggests that one may consider $p = dL(v)/dv$ as a possible solution which must also equal $m^2/c^2 v/L$. This then yields:

$$dL/dv = -m^2/c^2 v/L \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Or } L = -m^2/c^2 \sqrt{1 - vv/c^2} \quad ((11))$$

Thus, ((9)) contains both a linear transformation from the Lorentz matrix, but at the same time the quadratic Lorentz invariant $EE = pp + m^2/c^2$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that $H = E = pv - L$ for a free relativistic particle may be mapped directly into a Lorentz transformation equation using (p, E) as the starting vector, $(-v, m^2/c^2)$ as the final vector. This shows that $L = -m^2/c^2 \sqrt{1 - vv/c^2}$ where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 - vv/c^2}$. Thus, for a free relativistic particle, special relativity seems to be contained within $H = pv - L$. One may then show that $dL/dv = p$. A priori, the relativistic equation, $p = gv$, anticipates the relation $dL/dv = p$ if $L(v) = -m^2/c^2 \sqrt{1 - vv/c^2}$. A quadratic form in vv appears naturally if one seeks invariants of the Lorentz transformation matrix, e.g. $m^2/c^2 = EE - pp$. In particular, $p = gv$ and $E = gm^2/c^2$ are consistent with $p = dL/dv = m^2/c^2 v/(-L)$.

Reference

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relationship Between Lagrangian Theory, Quadratic Forms and Special Relativity for a Free Particle (preprint, zenodo, 2024)